

HIGH-EFFICIENT ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORD GENERATION THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING TASKS

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Abstract

The creation of Electronic Health Records (EHRs) was the study's goal. The EHR data produced will be more accurate than the data produced by the medGAN method. Medical layer 1 with Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) (medL1GAN) and medical layer 2 GAN (medL2GAN) were created after modifying medGAN, and the output from the three models was compared. Multi parameter Intelligent Monitoring in Intensive Care - III (MIMIC-III) and the National Health Insurance Research Database (NHIRD) were the two databases that we used. First, we used these three 3 models to train the models and produce EHRs. The effectiveness of the models was then assessed and contrasted using Machine Learning (ML): Association Rule (AR) prediction and mining. Thorough examination and discovered that our designs were sufficiently efficient for producing EHR data. The proposed models outscored medGAN with medL2GAN doing the best. Effectively creating realistic EHRs is possible with the proposed models can be trained on the data distribution of real EHRs. The proposed model used to improve the performance measures when compared with existing system.

Keywords: Electronic Health Records; Machine Learning; Generation Model; Medical Dataset; Association Rule Mining

1. Introduction

Early diagnosis is necessary for these life-threatening conditions to receive the right care and recover. The cost of diagnosing cancer and heart disease is error-prone, and time-consuming[1]. In the past, disease forecasting depended more on doctor knowledge than it does on hidden symptom patterns in healthcare data. Consequently, this could result in a misdiagnosis for medical purposes, which would then cause improper hospital services, driving up healthcare expenditures by lowering the standard of care given to patients [2–3]. Major hospitals use EHR systems to maintain digital data. It keeps a tremendous quantity of patient data [4]. Data collected in hospitals may be used for healthcare analytics and service enhancement through data mining.

Association rule mining is a well-known technique for data mining that identifies connections between symptoms and illnesses[5]. Association rule mining is used in the health industry for a variety of purposes, such as predicting illness based on a patient's condition, finding the best course of treatment for diseases, identifying pharmaceutical reactions, and enhancing clinical fraudulent activities using data mining [6].IF-THEN rules are generated using association rule mining and are easily understood by medical practitioners. To assess the severity of a disease, this technique is widely used by medical professionals and researcher is the best course of therapy based on the

diagnosis [7]. As a result, the healthcare system becomes significantly more price and treatment effective. Until recently, just one clinic's EHR system could be used to mine association rules from patient information [8]. A single electronic medical record only could hold a certain number of customer information.

Risky diseases necessitate stricter rules of the association. The confidence in association rule mining can be increased by combining all EHR system data on a single server and accuracy [9]. Healthcare poses a threat to patient privacy, in the local EHR system, patient information must be kept private. Data must be shared among various EHR systems while maintaining confidentiality for data mining to be accurate. To safeguard privacy, medicinal scientists have focused on mining association rules on dispersed health information [10–11].

The most important study project is protected and confidentiality-dependent association rule mining, which is carried out by many company organizations to first share the recurrent, amusing pattern, and then to draw that out [12]. As a result, by extracting useful info, economic growth may proceed on the right path. The implementation of a new structure that can offer operations both confidentiality and security for those who want to share transaction data details with other company employees, is the main goal of this study methodology [13].

2. Related Works

The advent of the Protection and Confidentiality conscious Large Database ARM ensures this research framework segments the data both horizontally and vertically using improved secured association rule mining. It is used to significantly protect sensitive data for a larger transaction database [14]. Data security is achieved through the use of k-Anonymization methods like suppression-based anonymization and generalization-based anonymization [15]. It is made used to safeguard confidential or sensitive data. To safeguard confidential data and enable hosting service providers to interact with the encrypted data, the Diffie-Hellman cryptosystem was finally developed [16]. By creating safe keys, the Diffie-Hellman algorithm is used to improve the system's general effectiveness, which in turn more effectively protects the real data.

In general, it is expected that ML algorithms are being used for a balanced dataset without taking the allocation of the classes into account before performing all of them. If the training dataset is severely skewed, this supposition may result in results with deceptive reliability [17]. A greater monitoring rate for one class than for other categories is the main reason for unbalanced data. The unbalanced data may result in a categorization that favors data that is majority-held and has several facets. However, classifiers may still be used on an unbalanced dataset [18]. However, as contrasted to unbalanced data, overall classification scores for even information are more precise. To mitigate the dangers of unbalanced data, resampling strategies are employed [19]. Replication of the datasets in the minority classes helps lessen this biased categorization. To eliminate bias toward the majority classes, the weighting of the minority classes is raised in randomized resampling by spontaneous replication of the minority classes without the addition of any new info [20].

In general, the under-sampling approach is better and more practical than random oversampling because the latter is more likely to result in additional issues with over-fitting and deceptive precision [21]. By replicating the initial data units, random oversampling generates an unwarranted increase in the training sample. As a result, random

oversampling expands the amount of data units without expanding the training dataset's diversity [22]. It is possible to unintentionally remove critical info, which is a significant downside of arbitrary oversampling. The synthetic minority oversampling technique and enhanced oversampling strategy substantially eliminate the issues caused by unexpected oversampling [23]. The amount of immediate neighbors serves as the foundation for the synthetic minority oversampling approach.

As a response, we incorporated information from the cooperative EHR systems that have been longitudinally segmented in our analysis. With this knowledge, we are aiming to establish international standards for associations while preserving the confidentiality of EHR systems throughout the world. A proposed method for assessing symptoms related to both fatal conditions uses data from the UCI collection on heart disease and breast cancer.

3. Proposed System

3.1 Data sets

We condensed to compare them fairly with medGAN, and the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes for each dataset were converted to 3-digit numbers. A patient's entry diagnosing history (MIMICIII and NHIRD) or treatments and actions as reflected within every field of the longitudinal EHR datasets shown by the patient. A patient will probably use a hospital more than once, hence the EHR data may have many entries for one patient. We combined into a single, fixed-sized vector of ICD codes all the longitudinal data for each patient. So, each dataset was represented as a multidimensional matrix, where each entry indicated a patient's information and each cell an individual ICD code. All count variables because sick people accumulate ICD codes. The tally parameters displayed the frequency with which a patient was associated with a specific ICD code. The first part of Table 1 shows a sample count dataset. An example binary dataset that was created from the equivalent count dataset is shown in Table 2. The Boolean parameters showed if or not a patient was connected to a certain ICD code.

Table 1: Sample count dataset

ID	ICD (817)	ICD (819)	ICD (363)
AAAAAA	3	2	0
BBBBB	0	0	0
CCCCCC	2	4	5
...	...	...	...
XXXXXX	1	0	4

Table 2: Sample binary dataset

ID	ICD (817)	ICD (819)	ICD (363)
AAAAAA	1	1	1
BBBBB	0	0	0
CCCCCC	1	1	0
...	...	...	...
XXXXXX	1	0	1

The goal of G's training technique is to deceive D or to increase the likelihood that D would commit an error by creating convincing false examples. This structure is like a two-player mini max game. An often-used comparison compares the discriminator to the police trying to find the fake currency and the generator to a forger trying to create illegal currency. Criminals want to make enough illegal currency that the authorities cannot tell the difference between it and real money. In contrast, the police are interested in finding fake currency as quickly as they can. The error signal from D is then used to train G by back propagation. The left portion of Figure 2 (a) depicts the central idea of the first GAN design. The decoder Dec is used to decode the generator G ($z_{\text{continuous}}$)'s output, as seen in Figure 2(b).

Instead of using the generic GAN in the proposed medL1GAN, we use the WGAN-GP, an upgraded generative network. The rest of the architecture is identical to the medGAN architecture seen in Figure 2. The Wasserstein GAN model, which was initially made, is said to use the weight-clipping approach, which allegedly results in low samples or, in some cases, the inability to converge, according to the creators of the WGAN-GP model. They proposed the gradient penalty technique of weight clipping as a substitute to address these problems. This method penalizes the discriminator's gradient norm relative to its input. Performance-wise, the WGAN-GP design outperforms various GAN designs, including the traditional WGAN. Therefore, in this study, we predicted that using medL1GAN to create EHRs would be more effective than using the existing medGAN.

Figure 2(a) GAN design

Figure 2(b) Original GAN and medGAN architecture.

3.2 Association Rule Mining in Distributed Data

The following is an explanation of association rule mining in horizontally segmented data: Let's say that EHR - fEHR1 is the case for the worldwide healthcare dataset EHR. The AR is written as $D = E$, where D , E , I , and $D E$ denote the dataset's collection of item sets, respectively. The applicability and attention level are represented by the confidence and support of the association rule. The association rule mining is illustrated by Algorithm 1 [24]. When the EHR system divulges a confidential parameter in step 5 of Algorithm 1, there has been a privacy issue. The proposed method calculates this overall support count while protecting anonymity.

Algorithm 1 Distributed Association Rule Mining

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Step 1:  $L_1 = \text{find frequent.1 - item set}(D)$ 
Step 2: for  $(k = 2; L_{k-1} \neq \emptyset; k + +)$ 
{
Step 3:  $C_k = \text{apriori. ger.}(L_{k-1});$ 
Step 4: for each candidate  $c \in C_k$ 
{
Step 5: collaboratively find the  $ac_{count}$ ;
Step 6:  $L_k = (c \in C_k | c.count \geq \text{min\_sup})$ 
}
}

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The n EHR systems participate in the cooperative mining of association rules by giving the central server access to medical data from the nearby EHR system. The base station grants them access to the pooled data mining findings. Using the information collected, the central server calculates association rules, which boosts the effectiveness of healthcare data mining across all institutions or helps medical professionals discover the connection between specific disorders and their symptoms.

3.3 Experimental setup

The testing dataset was set aside for testing the prediction models. The majority of the medGAN attribute values were carried over into our designs. Table 3 lists a few of the typical configurations. Our training data were further divided into subsets for validation and training using a 9:1 ratio. Using the training subset, we train the auto encoder beforehand for 100 iterations. About binary variables and count variables, respectively, binary-cross entropy and mean squared error, every epoch's validation and training loss is reported. 100 epochs are enough, and there is no overfitting, as shown by the training curve [25].

Table 3: Experimental settings

MIMIC-III sample count	37 214
Extended MIMIC-III training sample count	33 776
NHIRD sample training count	400 128
Pre-train the auto encoder count	100
Train the model count	1000
Size of batch	1000
Size of Generator	(128, 128, 128)
Size of Discriminator	(256, 128, 1)

To evaluate how inter-dimensional linkages are retained in data, We employed dimension-wise prediction and association rule mining. For example, is commonly employed in EHR information to uncover connections and easily understood patterns across clinical information, drugs, and diagnostic tests. This rule-based machine learning approach was used to uncover some strong connections or relationships between parameters in both actual and collections. We examined to see if the equivalent dataset contained the same relationships that were found in the real data set[26].

We did a forecasting task for every ICD code to evaluate inter dimensional correlations in the data in a roundabout way. We employed three prominent ML approaches for predictive modeling on EHR data: random forest, logistic regression, and support vector machine [27].We examined the plane of reality prediction outcomes of data-trained forecasting analytics with the real data's corresponding analytics.

4. Results and discussions

As a result, we tested numerous characteristics with minimal support of 5% to 10% and confidence of 40% to 50%. We obtained nearly identical findings when analyzing inter-dimensional correlations between actual information and data in all scenarios; so, we selected to display one expected outcome (refer to Table 4) below that created around 50200 rules using genuine datasets.

Table 4: Comparison of ARM with existing system

Dataset type	Real data extracted rules	GAN model	Synthetic data extracted rules	Synthetic rules with matched rule	Precision	Recall
MIMIC-III	73	medGAN	182	62	0.3389	0.8473
		medWGAN	65	53	0.8126	0.7225
		medBGAN	154	68	0.4380	0.9304
Extended MIMIC-III	155	medGAN	275	135	0.4892	0.8702
		medWGAN	202	144	0.7065	0.9222
		medBGAN	230	152	0.6552	0.9742
NHIRD	64	medGAN	1352	57	0.0415	0.8889
		medWGAN	63	52	0.8065	0.7937
		medBGAN	522	62	0.1155	0.9525

Figure 3 depicts the size-based forecast accuracy of the 3 probabilistic models derived from the logical regression model results trained on extended MIMIC-III, MIMIC-III, and NHIRD binary data, as well as the matching actual data. The scatter plots show one ICD code per dot. The logistic regression model's F1 scores, which were determined using actual binary data, are represented on the x-axis, and the logistic regression model's F1 scores, obtained after training on binary data, are displayed on the y-axis. Referring to the extended MIMIC-III binary data in Figure 5(b) and the MIMIC-III binary data in Figure 5(a), respectively, the prediction results for both sets of data and Both medL1GAN and medL2GAN perform better than medGAN for NHIRD binary data in Figure 5(c). Of all the generative models, medL2GAN stands out for performing the best.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: Results from the logistic regression model's scatter plots for dimension-wise prediction (F1-scores)

For each dataset evaluation criterion, the table shows the top model. In every evaluation, our models—medL2GAN or medL1GAN—perform better than the starting model, medGAN. The enhancement that the proposed models offer was insignificant in only a small number of cases, the Results section mentions; For both count data and binary, we did, however, typically achieve impressive results. The proposed models should be contrasted. only when testing counts data with the medL1GAN outperform medL2GAN for MIMIC-III data ARM and all remaining evaluations show that medL2GAN produces the best results. Contrarily, medL2GAN performs best in NHIRD data in all but the prediction of count data, where it falls short. But medL1GAN only saw a small improvement. Each model performs more effectively than the others in association rule mining, depending on the viewpoint.

medL1GAN occasionally performs similarly to medL2GAN or shows only minor improvements, here, using how many dimensions in the data are all zeros overall performance from a different angle. The models could have produced data for these dimensions that contained some dimensions that were all zero. These statistics are listed in Table 5 demonstrating that the count-variable-containing datasets ,in comparison to medGAN ARM, medL2GAN ARM, and medL1GAN ARM produce a greater number of dimensions with all zeros.

Table 5: All-zero dimensions

Dataset	(Total dimensions: 944) MIMIC-III	(Total dimensions: 1652) Extended MIMIC-III	(Total dimensions: 1017) NHIRD
Original data	6 (0.65%)	27 (1.58%)	5 (0.48%)
medGAN synthetic data with ARM	325(34.42%)	622(37.57%)	173(16.96%)
medWGAN synthetic data with ARM	608(64.45%)	1136(68.76%)	695(68.38%)
medBGAN synthetic data with ARM	164(17.32%)	454(28.02%)	129(12.62%)

Through the use of improved GANs, this research aims to construct realistic and practical discrete EHR data. Along with the fundamental statistical analysis, we used three well-known machine learning techniques in this extensive work for association rule mining, one popular technique for predictive modeling, and both. In terms of their quantity, origin, and scarcity, the three different EHR datasets used for the entire study were extended MIMIC-III, MIMIC-III, and NHIRD. Although we did not use any diagnosis-specific data, our proposed method is not limited to these. Furthermore, the initial GAN-based techniques deliver good results for producing continuous data. Because of this, any realistic EHR data can be generated using our model in a general sense, including data from fields other than medicine.

5. Conclusions

It may be easier for real EHR data to be obtained for research purposes if we use our generated data. The development of technology and medical science is expected to be significantly accelerated by this research. Since data are generated artificially, as we discussed in the first part, real and data do not explicitly map to one another. As a result, ARM infer from the intuition that our produced data continues to be resistant to re-identification. More significantly, based on the dataset's presence disclosure and attributed disclosure, the privacy risks associated with medGAN were formally evaluated. According to the privacy tests, medGAN ARM creates a variety of samples that give little information. Since we employed a medGAN ARM framework, our models preserve privacy.

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